

A STUDY ON CONSUMER ATTITUDE TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Organic food production is a self-regulated industry with government oversight in some countries, distinct from private gardening. Currently, the European Union, the United States, Canada, Japan, and many other countries require producers to obtain special certification based on government-defined standards in order to market food as organic within their borders. In the context of these regulations, foods marketed as organic are produced in a way that complies with organic standards set by national governments and international organic industry trade organizations. The need of the study is that demand is growing as incidences of food adulteration are repeatedly reported on in global media and consumer consciousness of natural, healthy and safe foods rises. The study is about analyzing the perception and attitude of customers towards organic food usage in Coimbatore. The main objective is to know the consumer awareness level of attitude towards organic food and to know the problems and issues faced by organic food. For this purpose a sample of 110 was collected with the respondents and factor analysis was used as a tool to analyze the data. The conclusion is that more awareness programs can be conducted to increase the awareness level of the customers about the organic foods which leads to increase in volume for the companies selling organic foods.

Key Words: Organic Food Production, Consumer Awareness & Training Programs

Introduction:

Organic foods are foods produced by methods that comply with the standards of organic farming. Standards vary worldwide; however, organic farming in general, features practices that strive to foster cycling of resources, promote ecological balance, and conserve biodiversity. Organizations regulating organic products may choose to restrict the use of certain pesticides and fertilizers in farming. In general, organic foods are also usually not processed using irradiation, industrial solvents or synthetic food additives.

Customer Attitude:

Consumer attitudes are a composite of a consumer's (1) beliefs about, (2) feelings about, (3) and behavioral intentions toward some object--within the context of marketing, usually a brand or retail store. These components are viewed together since they are highly interdependent and together represent forces that influence how the consumer will react to the object.

Objectives of the Study:

Primary Objective:

- ✓ To study the level of acceptance of various factors related to organic food.

Secondary Objectives:

- ✓ To know the consumer awareness level of attitude towards organic food.
- ✓ To know the problems and issues faced by organic food.
- ✓ To know the demographic profile of the respondents.

Scope of the Study:

The study is about analyzing the perception and attitude of customers towards organic food usage on Coimbatore. This may help the manufacturers related to organic food to develop themselves related to production and marketing strategy which will lead to increase in profit of their firm.

Research Methodology:

Methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem by appealing the various research techniques along with the logic behind the problem. Thus research methodology is a scientific way of solving the research problem. The area of the study is Coimbatore city only. For the purpose of this study the data were collected from 110 respondents using random sampling technique through Questionnaire. Percentage analysis and factor analysis are the tools used in this study.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Due to time constraint, the sample size is limited to 110 & the study area is restricted to Coimbatore.
- ✓ Respondent may fail to express their opinions and beliefs.
- ✓ There may be a bias in collecting the data.

Analysis and Interpretation:

		Frequency	Percent
Age of the Respondents	Below 20 years	77	70
	21-30 Years	33	30
	Total	110	100
Gender of the Respondents	Male	68	61.8
	Female	42	38.2
	Total	110	100
Educational Qualification of the Respondents	Illiterate	7	6.4
	Up to School	35	31.8
	Graduate	58	52.7
	Others	10	9.1
	Total	110	100
Level of Acceptance Towards Reliability of Organic Products	Agree	48	43.6
	Neutral	27	24.5
	Disagree	19	17.3
	Strongly Disagree	16	14.5
	Total	110	100
Level of Acceptance Towards Better Quality	Strongly Agree	11	10
	Agree	45	40.9
	Neutral	33	30
	Disagree	12	10.9
	Strongly Disagree	9	8.2
	Total	110	100
Level of Acceptance Towards Tastier	Strongly Agree	12	10.9
	Agree	28	25.5
	Neutral	34	30.9
	Disagree	18	16.4
	Strongly Disagree	18	16.4
	Total	110	100
Level of Acceptance Towards Easy Available	Strongly Agree	11	10
	Agree	35	31.8
	Neutral	29	26.4
	Disagree	28	25.5
	Strongly Disagree	7	6.4
	Total	110	100
Level of Acceptance Towards Nutrition Value	Strongly Agree	7	6.4
	Agree	46	41.8
	Neutral	34	30.9
	Disagree	23	20.9
	Total	110	100
Level of Acceptance Towards Very Expensive	Strongly Agree	16	14.5
	Agree	27	24.5
	Neutral	44	40

	Disagree	20	18.2
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.7
	Total	110	100
Frequency of Purchasing Food Products	Very Often	8	7.3
	Once in a Week	49	44.5
	Once in a Month	31	28.2
	Rarely	22	20
	Total	110	100
Place of Purchasing Organic Products	Departmental Store	9	8.2
	Super Market	37	33.6
	Online	38	34.5
	Others	26	23.6
	Total	110	100
Kind of Food Products Bought by the Respondents	Vegetables	4	3.6
	Fruits	55	50
	Cereals and Cereal Products	32	29.1
	Others	19	17.3
	Total	110	100
Person Influencing to Buy Organic Products	Friends and Relatives	18	16.4
	Newspaper	38	34.5
	Television	40	36.4
	Others	14	12.7
	Total	110	100

Factor Analysis:

Acceptance of Consumers towards Organic Food Products:

A total of 16 variables were identified for the purpose of collecting acceptance of consumers towards organic food products. In order to reduce the number of variables and to identify the key factors contributing towards the acceptance, factor analysis is performed. KMO and Bartlett's test is conducted to identify the sampling adequacy.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.569
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1.071
	Df	105
	Sig.	.000

KMO of sampling adequacy value for the acceptance measures is 0.569 and it indicates that the sample was adequate to consider the data as normally distributed. Rotated component matrix is used to identify the factors after data reduction. The results are shown below,

Rotated Component Matrix^a					
	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Level of acceptance towards reliability of organic products	.165	.063	.745	.139	.032
Level of acceptance towards better quality	.078	.260	.186	.786	.009
Level of acceptance towards tastier	.037	.818	.120	.203	-.017
Level of acceptance towards easy available	.150	.787	-.038	.312	-.169
Level of acceptance towards nutrition value	.884	.178	.106	.024	.089
Level of acceptance towards very expensive	.615	.310	.055	-.157	.537
Level of acceptance towards providing healthier food for them and their family by purchasing organic products	.831	.060	.171	-.123	-.213
Level of acceptance towards organic food taste better than non organic food	.710	.006	.046	.437	.048
Level of acceptance towards purchasing organic products means they support local farmers and agriculture	.213	-.034	.830	-.298	-.010

Level of acceptance towards organic foods carrying about environment	.501	-.121	.442	-.518	.291
Level of acceptance towards fertilize free of organic means	-.045	.202	.763	.330	-.186
Level of acceptance towards lower price for organic food	.569	.295	.217	.105	.569
Level of acceptance towards wider product selection for organic food	.132	.865	.186	-.213	.148
Level of acceptance towards strong influence from friends	.128	.536	-.117	.298	-.332
Level of acceptance towards healthiness of organic foods based on scientific evidence	.081	.344	.241	.028	-.794
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.					
a. Rotation converged in 8 iterations.					

Interpretation:

The common factors above 0.5 can be taken for decision making process of the study. The factors are Level of acceptance towards better quality, level of acceptance towards tastier, Level of acceptance towards nutrition value, level of acceptance towards providing healthier food for them and their family by purchasing organic products, level of acceptance towards purchasing organic products means they support local farmers and agriculture, and level of acceptance towards wider product selection for organic food.

Conclusion:

More awareness and training programs can be given to the customers so that awareness about the organic foods can be increased which leads to increase in volume for the companies selling organic foods. Package of the product: Provide a good packing facilities to specific product can be made by the companies. It is important to develop more marketing area as there is no regulated market facility in organic product.

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